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Building the "Erasmus+ Program" of Beijing: Taking the Beijing higher education joint cultivation program as an example

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Abstract

In the cross-region, cross-domain and cross-culture educational practices of cultivating composite high-quality talents with innovation, inclusiveness and understanding, the "Erasmus+ program" in Europe provides us with an excellent sample. Compared to "Erasmus+ program", the "Beijing Higher Education Joint Cultivation Program" has achieved significant results in fully activating Beijing's higher education resources, cultivating innovative high-level talents, strengthening much more cooperation among participated universities, and providing comprehensive services for Beijing's higher education reform and social-economic development. Both from the perspective of urban development positioning and the trend of higher education development, the implementation of Beijing Higher Education Joint Cultivation Program in the future should continue to innovate on the dimensions of mobility building, higher education capacity building, and regional higher education integration, and truly create an innovative brand of higher education in Beijing.

Keywords: Beijing Higher Education Joint Cultivation Program; Mobility, education capacity building; Integration of regional higher education

1. Introduction

"The Medici Effect" is a common category in discussions about business models and management. In terms of talent cultivation in higher education area, its greatest inspiration to us is to cultivate composite high-quality talents with innovation, inclusiveness and understanding in a cross-region, cross-domain and cross-culture educational process. For these above, the "Erasmus+ program" in Europe provides us with excellent reference. In response to the trend of talent exchange and internationalization in training, as well as the integration process of the European Community, the European Union launched the Erasmus Program in 1987, which was the first European student mobility scholarship program. In 2004, the European Union launched the Erasmus Mundus World (2004-2013), which extended cooperation beyond Europe. In January 2014, European Union launched the "Erasmus+ program", providing a large amount of funding for the mobility of people, sponsoring many kinds of students and educators to study abroad, and continuing to promote cross-university and cross-border partnerships and education policy reform. This has set an excellent benchmark for the reform of higher education in Beijing.

In fact, Beijing has taken some actions in the above-mentioned areas. Around 2015, based on the urban development positioning of Beijing, in order to provide strong talent support, intellectual support, and innovation support for the international first-class harmonious and livable city, a series of measures were launched for the development of higher education in Beijing. As colleges of different levels have different historical accumulation and advantages, therefore, the cooperation and interaction between different universities in Beijing is extremely important for urban development. So among series of measures, the "Beijing Higher Education Joint Cultivation Program" (hereinafter, "JCP") was one of the

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important measures aimed at coordinating and enlarging the open sharing of high-quality educational resources, deepening the cooperation mechanism between different levels of universities, and promoting the integration of science, education, industry, and education. The JCP is launched by Beijing Municipal Education Commission, and is jointly built and implemented by state-owned universities and municipal universities of Beijing. More than ten high-tech and frontier subjects which are prioritized for development in Beijing (such as information technology, medicine and health, financial technology services, etc) , have been selected for the program. In the first three years, students receive education and training in state-owned universities and obtain a completion. After they return back to the municipal universities in the fourth year, JCP students need to complete their graduation programs would finally obtain the graduation certificate of the municipal universities. From 2015 to 2023, 17 municipal universities and 23 state-owned universities have joined in the program and carried out joint construction, with an average annual scale of over 1000 students. Up to 2024, more than 10,000 students have participated in it. Compared with the program goals, JCP has achieved very good results. Meanwhile, compared to the "Erasmus+ program", JCP also has many areas needed to be improved and developed.

2. Current practices and effectiveness of JCP

At present, there are mainly two kinds of management mode of the JCP according to recent research. [1] In the first mode, the program is generally led by the existing functional departments such as the Academic Affairs Office or Student Affairs Office of the school. And the visiting students are educated and managed in specific schools. According to the survey, the vast majority of state-owned universities adopt this model. Another approach is to establish a separate school, such as Beijing College, to implement educational training or program promotion. In this case, visiting students are taught separately from students of the same major in the state-owned universities most of the time. Central University of Finance and Economics(hereinafter, "CUFE") established Beijing College in 2016, but unlike other Beijing colleges, visiting students receive the same resources and full immersion educating in each professional colleges the same as the ordinary students of the college in CUFE. And Beijing College is responsible for streamlining the program mechanism and promoting the smooth implementation of the program as the overall coordinator of the program. Below, we intends to take Beijing College of CUFE as an example to systematically review the implementation process and effectiveness of JCP in Beijing.

Firstly, as a collaborative hub, Beijing college of CUFE reduced the workload and cost of cross communications for program participators by being the one-stop service center. It also effectively solved student related difficulties. By this way, it makes professional colleges to concentrate on talent cultivation, and makes students concentrate on receiving high-quality education. On one hand, the program is operated very well by rationalizing the management mode, clarifying the rights and responsibilities between stakeholders in the direct collaborative management process of various units. More specifically, CUFE clarified the basic process of temporary student enrollment management, academic warning and disciplinary handling, emergency response, and other matters. In one word, by acting as a "propeller" for overall program, Beijing college built a good work linkage mode of "precise division of labor and high collaboration". On another hand, in terms of collaboration between universities, Beijing college leads the signing of a tripartite agreement to clarify the rights and responsibilities of all parties involved, and establish institutional regulations for the healthy development of the program. At the same time, through regular visits, continuous organization of seminars and talent training achievement reports, the cooperation and communication between two parties are largely deepened and intensified. What's more, in solving problems related to students, Beijing college provides timely feedback and precise strategies to efficiently solve the problems and difficulties the students encountered. Acting as an accelerator for problem-solving, CUFE creates a more friendly environment and atmosphere for visiting.

Secondly, CUFE systematically optimize the education and teaching training mechanism. On the one hand, in response to the academic foundation, learning characteristics, and talent demand direction of program students, CUFE comprehensively customize and optimize teaching design and implementation, find a scientific training positioning that matches the overall situation of students, set a four-year integrated professional training plan, set reasonable professional difficulty, and appropriately increase the proportion and opportunities of combining professional learning with social and enterprise practical operations. So that we can integrate the orientation of cultivating innovative and applied talents into the entire training process. On the other hand, it is necessary to focus on the group of students with academic difficulties by establishing an early intervention mechanism or helping them increase educational engagement through phased or batch guidance.

Thirdly, it's really crucial to continuously improve the monitoring and analysis mechanism for student growth and program development. CUFE builds a comprehensive tracking and analysis system for the students, grasp student dynamics, and explore potential pain points or growth points. In order to fully tap into the big data of student growth

and development, summarize experiences lessons, CUFE conducts enrollment surveys for new students, annual growth and development surveys and feedback surveys at the end of program. By this way, CUFE can use data to achieve a dynamic development portrait of students, present the effectiveness of talent cultivation, and finally improve program design and implementation.

Finally, CUFE refines the comprehensive development mechanism for students in all aspects. One is to establish and optimize the student honor reward and funding system, such as kinds of scholarships. On the basis of exploring the establishment of a multi category, customized incubation and funding system based on the interests, specialties, professional abilities and segmented groups. It can encourage students to achieve an all-round development based on each interests and advantages. The second is to enhance the international communication skills of JCP. To meet the needs of Beijing's economic and social development, Beijing college tried to explore international overseas platforms or course offerings to encourage JCP students to actively participate in overseas exchanges, internships, visits, etc. The third is to guide the establishment of student organizations specifically targeting the JCP student group. It's really important for visiting students to achieve their self-serving and self-managing. So Beijing college does not only help them establish JCP students union for visiting students, but also establish JCP alumni organization for those graduated JCP students. Such actions greatly benefit them for their group communication, information sharing, platform construction and cultural shaping. Vice versa, such approaches finally give a push to optimize the program management and development.

Through the above measures and collaborative efforts of all parties involved in the program, JCP of CUFE has been steadily implemented for nearly 9 years, with a total number of over 1100 visiting students. JCP allows students to fully enjoy the high-quality teaching resources of state-owned universities, experience the campus culture and atmosphere without discrimination. It creates a sense of belonging based on both universities. Students have a high recognition of their major and a solid foundation of professional knowledge. After graduation, more than one-third of them choose to be an undergraduate student in China or abroad. Compared with students with same majors in municipal universities, the results and willingness of pursuing graduate degree for JCP students show a higher proportion and data. During the visiting period, students have comprehensively developed various skills and abilities, and the number of students who have received relevant awards at the provincial level or above is higher than that of students in municipal universities. In one word, the JCP has a significant effect on improving students' general abilities. What's more, JCP students do not only have a high overall satisfaction with the program, the overall feedback from the governmental authority and municipal universities is also rather excellent. The education reputation and praise of CUFE is also obtained a rapid improvement.

3. Program considerations in the dimensions of urban development and educational trends

Firstly, we should focus on the talent demand in urban development. According to the Overall Plan of Beijing City (2016-2035), the city of Beijing aims to be a national political center, cultural center, international communication center and technical innovation center. Regarding to specific goals for talent cultivation according to Long-term Outline of Capital Talent Development Plan (2010-2020) and Capital Education Modernization 2035, Beijing needs to enhance its support capabilities driven by scientific and technological innovation. Through heuristic, exploratory, participatory, and cooperative teaching, efforts should be made to achieve the comprehensive development of students in morality, intelligence, physical fitness, aesthetics, and labor. The abilities of observing, discovering, analyzing and problem-solving should be cultivated. The appearance of large number of innovative and high skilled talents will meet the demand for emerging cutting-edge industries in Beijing. Talking back to JCP, it is expected to cultivate large number of talents to serve the development of Beijing. At the same time, with the help of state-owned universities in program cooperation, the education capacity of municipal universities is also expected to be improved rapidly.

The second dimension is educational practice under circumstance of cross-domain knowledge production. The visiting process of JCP students is a highly distinctive educational practice. It's not only a cross-campus joint education, but also a kind of collective interaction with cross-ranking features. All these above lead the JCP to be a highly exemplary educational case. It was once said that, although the participation of diverse educational cultures and campus atmospheres can indeed enhance the adaptability and inclusiveness of learners, mixing different levels of learning ability groups will meanwhile lower the quality of outstanding individuals and dampen the intrinsic motivation of students with learning difficulties. But actually that's not the case. On the one hand, more evidences have shown that by integrating educated groups with different manifestations, setting reasonable educational goals and adopting flexible educational methods, educational increments can be formed for all levels of learners within same group. On the other hand, from the perspective of courses as a key of knowledge production processes, the true curriculum should be "practical courses".[2: 27-30] Its starting point is not the structure of knowledge, but how knowledge is produced by

people who are jointly active. Knowledge is no longer regarded as private property passed down from academic discoverers to distribute and transmit, it should be a product of collaborative work between teachers and students. This idea of not focusing on established knowledge structures and levels, but focusing on involving teachers and students in interactive knowledge creation, can enhance students' sense of acquisition better. In addition, from the perspective of educational philosophy, education acquisition is the result of the comprehensive effect of capital, circumstances and habit. [3:118-122] The movement of creating "inferior students" by segmentation of capital, distortion of the circumstances and habitual anchoring should be avoided. It should also be rejected from labeling the educated who temporarily have learning difficulties. The attention should be paid to inclusive fields and equal interaction to promote mutual learning and teaching.

The third thing is about the improvement direction in program comparison. At present, the "Erasmus+ program" mainly includes three key actions (KA), including the EU Lifelong Learning Program, Youth In Action, and Five international cooperation programs. In addition to providing opportunities for joint training of master's and doctoral students in Europe and around the world through the plan, the packed projects also aim to enhance the quality of vocational education, basic education, teacher training and adult education in EU members. The projects also hope to support the establishment of strategic partnerships between universities, government agencies and enterprises in participating countries, the establishment of knowledge alliances and industry technology alliances, and ultimately achieve the goals of supporting the reform of education policies, improving policy transparency and evaluating the effects of government policy reforms. Compared with the Erasmus+ programme, there are still much more to be improved for the JCP operation. For example, the first is to continue to improve the capacity building of program mobility. Building of both teaching resource mobility and human resource mobility are all important indicator that the JCP has always paid attention to. The construction of this kind of mobility capacity not only needs to further rationalize and optimize the cooperation and collaboration mechanism of stakeholders, but also needs to further improve the quality of curriculum teaching, improve the whole process of education, develop novel and innovative courses, and improve the level of ability and skill transfer.

To achieve that, it is also important to timely summarize the characteristics and achievements of both entire program and visiting students, expand social influence. What's more, it is also necessary to promote the research on teaching models and ideological education systems for the JCP. The second is to further strengthen the construction of higher education capacity. In supporting the modernization, innovation and popularization of higher education, it is necessary to respond to various challenges prudently on the basis of program, adapting to the needs of the labor market, equal opportunities, plan and cross-campus executing. State-owned universities should strengthen the co construction with municipal universities in the modernization of curriculum development, higher education institution governance and educational management. Through joint action and sharing of good practices, supporting for policy reform and modernization improvement of higher education governance could finally come true. Specifically, we can try to take the construction of virtual teaching and research rooms and the co-construction of related majors as the starting point, take efforts to promote the sharing of teaching resources, systems and methods, etc. Beyond of this, JCP participators maybe can jointly apply for some research projects or educational awards in order to explore new growth points for cooperation, and enhance the higher education capabilities of both sides. The third is to explore the substantial construction of regional higher education integration community. Like the "Erasmus+ program", JCP has always actively advocated for excellence and equality at the same time. In the past 8 years, it has achieved remarkable results in stimulating the vitality of the labor market, promoting academic exchange, and enhancing students' awareness of serving Beijing's development. However, on the one hand, the beneficiaries of JCP, either students or universities are still far away from sufficiency. There is still big gap in building a true knowledge alliance and creating integrated practices and cultural concepts for Beijing city. In addition to talent cultivation, there are strong needs to continuously improve the alliance between educational organization and related industries. And many things still need to be done for participants to engage in cross campus practices with more civic awareness and innovative thinking or skills.

4. Conclusion

As a typical case of serving for the development of the economy and society in Beijing, JCP has always been aiming at expanding education openness and cultivating innovative, compound, and applied talents for capital Beijing. It explored the "top-notch innovative talent training mode" and "joint talent training" model, and is really a concrete practice according to Education Reform and Development Outline of Beijing for Medium and Long Term(2010-2020). In one word, JCP has actually been the Erasmus+ Program of Beijing. And in the past 8 years, JCP also actually has had a positive impact on high-quality talent cultivation and win-win cooperation among universities. Looking forward to the futures, either from the perspective of urban development positioning or the trend of higher education development, the implementation of JCP should continue to innovate from the dimensions of mobility building, higher education capacity building, and regional higher education integration, truly creating an innovative brand of higher education of Beijing.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

Authors have declared no conflict of interest exists.

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